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Time Management, Study Environment And Note-Taking Technique On Academic Performance Among Senior Secondary School Students In Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria

¹Fehintola, J.O. PhD & ²Dr M. O. E. Olorunda

¹Department of Counselling & Human Development Studies,
University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria.

E-Mail:fehintola.j@dic.ui.edu.ngiof677@yahoo.com/ joseph.fehintola@gmail.com

Tel No: 08162023919/ 08056240315

²Department of Nursing, Lead City University, Ibadan, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

This study is based on study environment, time management and note-taking techniques on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ibadan. Descriptive research design of correlational type was used for the study. A sample of 200 senior secondary school students was drawn using simple random sampling technique. The name of the schools are Immanuel High School, University of Ibadan, Immanuel Grammar School, University of Ibadan and Methodist High School, Ibadan. The data were collected using Standard four standardized questionnaires. Three research questions were raised and tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson's product moment correlation and multiple regression analysis. It was discovered that time management ($r=0.586$), study environment ($r=0.983$) and note-taking technique ($r=0.243$) have significant relationship to academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan. Independent variables jointly accounted for 96.7% of the total variance that occurred to academic performance. Findings revealed that of all the independent variables, in terms of magnitude of the contribution, time management ($\beta = 0.444$, $t = 5.673$, $p < 0.05$) was the most potent contributor to academic performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Ibadan followed by the study environment ($\beta = 0.169$, $t = 2.066$, $p < 0.05$) while Note-taking technique ($\beta = 0.169$, $t = 2.026$, $p < 0.05$) was the least potent. Therefore, regular counselling services to train students on time management, note-taking skills should be advocated in order to boost their study habit and enhance their academic performance. Government should also allocate resources to improve school facilities and create conducive learning environment. The researchers concluded that time management, note-taking skills and study environment are germane to academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria.

Keywords: Academic performance, Time management, Study environment, Note taking Techniques, senior secondary school students in Ibadan.

INTRODUCTION

Academic performance is undoubtedly a research drive at the heart of educators, teachers, counselling psychologists, policy makers, parents and guardians, social workers etc. in their attempts to investigate

what determines academic outcomes of learners, they have come up with more questions than answers. It is an issue that deeply concerns all stakeholders of education not only in our country, but also in many other countries and continents. The social and economic development of any country is directly linked with students' performance. The students' performance plays an important role in producing the best quality graduates who will become great leader and provide manpower for the country that are responsible for the country's economic and social development. Education in general is one of the commanding aspects that not only inculcates the essential skills, abilities and knowledge among the individuals, but also leads to overall growth, development and progress of the individuals, community and the nation at large. To achieve the social and economic development of any nation, education should be giving adequate attention and there should be an improvement in the students' performance.

The complexity of the academic performance starts from its conceptualization. Sometimes it is known as school readiness, academic achievement and school performance, but generally the difference in concepts is only explained by semantics as they are used as synonyms. Conventionally, it has been agreed that academic performance should be used in university populations and school performance in regular and alternative basic education populations. Several authors agree that academic performance is the result of learning, prompted by the teaching activity by the teacher and produced by the student. From a humanistic approach, Martinez (2007) states that academic performance is "the product given by the students and it is usually expressed through school grades"

The tracking of academic performance fulfils a number of purposes. Areas of achievement s and failure in a student's academic career need to be evaluated in order to foster improvement and make full use of the learning process. Results provide a framework for talking about how students fare in school and a constant standard to which all student are held, performance results also allow student to be ranked and sorted holding teachers and schools accountable for the component of each and every grade. Performance in school is grading students demonstrate their knowledge by taking written and oral test, performing presentation, turning in homework and participating in class activities/discussion. Teacher evaluation in the form of letter or number grades and side notes to describe how well a student has done. At the level, students are evaluated by their performance on standardized tests geared towards specific ages and based on a set of achievement of students in each age group are expected to meet (Chel 2011, Adekoye, 2011).

For Caballero (2017), academic performance involves meeting goals, achievements and objectives set in the program or course that a student attends. These are expressed through grades which are the result of an assessment that involves passing or not certain tests, subjects or courses. On their part, Torres and Rodríguez (Willcox, 2011) define academic performance as the level of knowledge shown in an area or subject compared to the norm, and it is generally measured using the grade point average. Grades are certainly the most well-known indicator of academic performance. Grades are the student's "score" for their classes and overall tenure. Grades are most often a tallying or average of assignment and test scores and may often be affected by different factors. Grading systems vary greatly by county and school; common scales include a percentage form 1-100, lettering systems from A-F, and grade point averages (GPA) from 0-4.0 or above.

Provision of quality education is a priority that every country will aspire to include amongst the national goals for development. According Kimani, Kara & Njagi (2013) the purpose of education is to equip the citizenry with values, skills and knowledge to reshape their society and eliminate inequality. This is because education helps an individual develop his/her capabilities, attitudes and behaviour that is acceptable to the society. The benefits of having quality education is that it is able to adapt to the changing needs of the country as the world changes and spearhead the development of human resource and the country's economy.

Educational institutions are mandated to use education as a tool for social transformation. The success of a school is measured by the quality of students it produces. The success of any educational institution is measured by the performance of its students in both academic and non-academic tests. This is supported by Yusuf (2018) when contending that the performance should not only be based in terms of test and examination results and student ability to apply what is learnt and the rate at which students move on to higher institution of learning, but should include other areas such as whether the students have acquired

the survival skills. In spite of that, the use of students' achievement in academic work to assess the teacher's effectiveness has gained ground. The measure of academic performance as a symbol of school success can be traced way back from the Victorian period (Bell, 2013). Since then, academic performance has been used to grade schools and most importantly to determine ones career paths. The 'good schools' are acclaimed to be those that are able groom the students well enough to achieve the set standards. This is measured by use of students' academic performance both at school level and nationally. The importance of students' high performance has attracted the attention of the public, policy-makers, educators, learners and ministry of education alike.

Academic performance of students is a key feature in education (Rono, 2013). It is considered to be the center around which the whole education system revolves. Narad and Abdullah (2016) opined that the academic performance of students determines the success or failure of any academic institution. Signh, Malik and Signh (2016) also argued that academic performance of students has a direct impact on the socio-economic development of a country. Similarly, Farooq, Chaudhry, Shafiq and Behanu (2011), asserted that students' academic performance serves as a bedrock for knowledge acquisition and the development of skills. Additionally, Farooq et al., (2011) emphasized that the top most priority of all educators is academic performance of students. According to Narad and Abdullah (2016) academic performance is the knowledge gained which is assessed by marks by a teacher and/or educational goals set by students and teachers to be achieved over a specific period of time. They added that these goals are measured by using continuous assessment or examinations results.

Observation showed that Oyo state which used to be noted for academic excellence in West Africa Examination Council (WAEC) in the past had declined from 1st -10th position to 4th position in 2013/2014 session. Results showed that between 2010 and 2017, only 17% of the students had English language while 36% Yoruba language, 20% Biology, 31% Mathematics and 26% Economics were successful in SSCE (Ministry of Education, Oyo State 2015). Besides, the results of students who sat for Senior Schools Certificate Examination (SSCE) between 2017 to 2022 also showed clearly the decline in the academic performance of secondary school students in Oyo State. In 2017, 2018 and 2019, the number of students who registered for SSCE conducted by West Africa Examination Council were 11,956, 11,011, 13,639 respectively. Only 23%, 29%, 25% had 5 credits including the core subjects such as Mathematics and English language while others failed. In 2020, the percentage of candidates that passed with at least five credits including Mathematics and English language were 38.68% (Punch Newspaper, 2021). While in 2022, candidates recorded 50% with five credits in Mathematics and English language which is still not encouraging. (Oyo State Ministry of Education, 2022). Upon the observations in the decline in the students' academic performance in public secondary schools in Oyo State, one begins to wonders if the persistence in the academic deterioration is not a reflection of teachers' poor classroom management in the schools. In other words, the observed poor academic performance of students could be as a result of teachers' ineffective classroom management.

Educational institutions have no worth without students. Indeed, that is to say students are the most essential assets for any educational institution (Sentamu, 2013). This view however becomes valid only when students' academic performance is good enough. Thus, grades awarded to individuals at the end of an academic study are important indicators of ability and productivity when those individuals look for their first jobs. In fact, a person's education is closely linked to his/her life chances, income and wellbeing (Battle & Lewis, 2012). Thus, students' success in any academic task has always been of special interest to educators, parents and society at large (Ajayi, 2006). The issue of factors affecting students' academic performance therefore remains a top priority to educators (Considine and Zappala, 2012).

The blame for poor academic performance among secondary school students could be attributable to avalanches of factors which can be within or outside the students involvement. These can be divided into factors that are inherent in the individuals and those that are outside the individual. One of those factors that can influence academic performance of students and of interest in this study is personality trait. Every human being is born with its distinctive and unique character from one individual to another, either in terms of behavior or personality. Personality is an individual's physical, emotional and cognitive qualities

(Rahimi, 2017) and personality is also one of the human unique factors. Each individual is unique and cannot be compared to others. According to Engler (2003), these differences exist due to the genetic and environmental factors. However, there are conflicts in this theory. Some believe that personality is formed due to genetic factors. Others argue that differences occur due to environmental factors (Robbins, 2010). However, different people at different times have passed the blame of poor performance in secondary school to students because of their low retention, parental factors, association with wrong peers, low achievement motivation and the like (Fehintola, 2014; Aremu & Oluwole 2001). Morakinyo (2003) and Fehintola, (2014) believed that the falling level of academic achievement is attributable to teacher factors. Others found out that the attitude of some teachers to their job is reflected in their poor attendance to lessons, lateness to school, unsavoury comments about student's performance that could damage their ego poor method of teaching and they like affect students' academic performance.

Time management is very important since it may actually affect students' overall performance and achievements. Time management means those behaviors that aim at achieving an effective use of time while performing certain goal-directed activities, Claessens, (2017). Time management relates to how individuals manage their time to suit their daily living or to make it flow steadily with their routines. Alghamdi (2018) believes that one must be restricted to a specified period of time to adjust with present and future situations. Time management is believed to play a vital role in improving students' academic performance and achievements in colleges. According to Brigitte, Claessens, (2015), each and every student should have time management ability which includes setting goals & priorities, using time management mechanism and being organized in using time.

Similarly, Macan, (2020) believe that the secret to achieving success in life is effective and efficient managing skills of this all-important resource called time. Accordingly, Seviri and Kandy (2011) posits that time management skills have an impact on student's academic achievement. Laurie & Hellsten, (2012) agree that a good time management skill boosts students' grades and enhances their productivity. Similarly, Kelly (2014) describes time management skills as quite essential to college students and as one of the keys to higher academic achievements. For effectiveness, Alsalmi, (2018) believes that college students must give priorities to some tasks over the others in order to distribute the sufficient time to get the best results. Time is the scarcest resource of the manager and if it is not managed, nothing else can be managed, Alex (2019).

Time and tide are believed wait for no man. Students need to make use of their time wisely as no one can hold the time back. Whatever one cannot achieve within a day will have to be carried over. There are many obstacles to achievement that can impede progress and performance of students. These include poor time management, bullying in school, deviant or anti-social behavior, poor parenting style or involvement etc. In the modern world, time is seen as an indefinitely divisible and usable commodity. It helps to infuse the concept of time through the institution. All the material and human resources possessed by organizations can be enhanced in the course of time or be transformed as time goes on; yet the only asset that cannot be changed or purchased or stored is time itself. The secret to achieving success in life is effectively managing this resource that everyone possesses equally and paying sufficient emphasis to planning (Macan, Shahani, Dipboye & Phillips, 2000).

Time management has to do with planning and scheduling activities, organizing tasks in a prioritized order and allocating time to the tasks according to their order of importance and helping one achieve desired objectives (Achunine, 1995). Time management is the ability to manage and control time (Lakein, 2003). The use of planners, calendars and the like are effective tools in managing time. Time management is the art of arranging organizing, scheduling and budgeting one's time for the purpose of generating more effective work and productivity (Lakein, 2003). In completing the task on schedule, a student will also enhance his academic performance. It can be deduced from Misra (2000) view that an in-school adolescent who spends his time on irrelevant things instead of concentrating on studies may end up having poor academic performance. The issue of students loitering about, holding parties at the expense of their studies tends to suggests that students do not manage their time well. Hence, academic performance might be affected.

Study environment encompasses learning resources and technology, means of teaching, modes of learning, and connections to societal and global contexts. The term also includes human behavioral and cultural dimensions, including the vital role of emotion in learning. The study environment is a composite of human practices and material systems, much as an ecology is the combination of living things and physical environment (Balog, 2018). Contemporary learners deserve learning spaces that meet their individual and collective needs. To meet this challenge, educational leaders must provide physical and cultural environments that are empowering and engaging (Orlu, 2013).

Study environments vary from classroom to classroom and context to context each with unique elements. According to study.com (2018) study environments can be learner-centered; knowledge - centered; assessment - centered; and community - centered. Learner-centered environments are designed for the active construction of knowledge by and for learners (Federation University, 2018). Knowledge-centered study environments are those which support students' deep investigations of big ideas through generative learning activities. Assessment-centered study environments provide frequent, ongoing, and varying opportunities for assessment, including opportunities for revision and self and peer assessment (Alvaro, 2010). Community-centered environments value collaboration, negotiation of meaning, respect for multiple perspectives around which knowledge is constructed, and connections to the local community and culture (Raccoon gang (2018).

Study environment is composed of some components that influence the student's learning curve. These components according to Balog (2018) include; people; teaching materials, technical tools, and learning resources; curriculum, training, and instruction, and physical environment/learning space. The people are the individuals that affect the student directly or indirectly through connection or relationship which can contribute to students' growth and success in their career aspect. The teaching materials, technical tools, and learning resources are the teaching materials, highly advanced tools or others instructional resources that are aligned with the curriculum as a part of student learning support. The curriculum, training, and instruction are the core foundations of the learning process; they influence one another and play vital roles to facilitate the flow of knowledge and delivery of instructional content/curriculum. The physical environment/learning space refers to the physical setting of the learner's environment which should evoke positive responses and hold the interests of those who inhabit it (Balog, 2018).

Mondal (2012) identified some important factors that may affect learning process to include Intellectual factor which refers to the individual mental level. Learning factors are factors owing to faulty methods of work or study, and narrowness of experimental background which may affect the learning process. Physical factors include health, physical development, nutrition, visual and physical defects, and glandular abnormality. Mental factors are attitudes like interest, cheerfulness, and open mindedness etc that are important in the development of personality. Personal factors, such as instincts and emotions, and social factors, such as cooperation and rivalry, are directly related to a complex psychology of motivation. The teacher as an individual personality is an important factor in the study environment. They are key factors that create a favorable teaching-learning milieu that will make the instructional process easy, enthusiastically adaptable and useful (Usman, 2016). The way in which his personality interacts with the personalities of the pupils helps to determine the kind of behavior which emerges from the learning situation (Brown, 2015). Environmental factors like classrooms, textbooks, equipment, school supplies, and other instructional materials etc. are the physical conditions needed for learning (Mondal, 2012).

Waldman (2016) observed that before students can succeed academically, they must feel safe, both physically and mentally, and to have a safe study environment, students must feel welcomed, supported, and respected. Personalizing learning helps students develop skills including thinking critically, using knowledge and information to solve complex problems, working collaboratively, communicating effectively, learning how to learn, and developing academic mindsets that would greatly increase students engagement (Raccoon gang , 2018). More so, students must feel connected to teachers, staff, and other students. Schools can nurture these connections by focusing on students' social and emotional learning (SEL). Students must also feel supported by all those connected to their learning experience like teachers, classmates, administrators, family, and community members for a higher academic feat (Waldman, 2016). Productive study environments are crucial to students' academic, emotional and social success in school.

A conducive study environment doesn't just happen on their own or by chance. They should be created through conscious procedures like interacting with students in a positive manner, exhibiting positive behaviors etc that would promote learning activities in the study environment (Becton, 2017).

One of the easiest ways to transfer what is heard from short-term memory to long-term memory is to include writing skills in the process. Setting four basic language skills to work together increases the effectiveness of learning and remembering. The use of note-taking habits as a writing activity while listening is an important component of the learning process. Note-taking is summarizing what one has understood in one's own words to remember it later. According to Piolat, Olive, and Kellogg (2005) annotation of what is listened to or read is often done haphazardly and the notes taken are limited by the speaking rate of the speaker. It is often thought that those who take a lot of notes get quality notes, but this often harms learning outcomes rather than benefiting them (Friedman, 2014). The reason for this situation is that most of the time while listening or reading, it is an effort to write down every statement in the source of the information.

Note-taking saves students from forgetting a speech or rereading an entire book. According to Hayati and Jalilifar (2009), the reason for this is the student's desire to get good notes. The best reason to encourage note-taking is the implementation of not replaying a speech and presentation. Students enjoy taking notes because not having to look at the relevant material again while preparing for the exam by taking notes means that they can save time and reduce cognitive load. Students may enjoy taking notes because they assume it will be easy to review material to prepare for a test or exam by taking notes. (Murtafi'ah, Asmiyah and Fitriah, 2020).

Notetaking is not writing exactly what is heard or read, but writing what is understood in a personal way. Piolat, Olive, and Kellogg (2005) stated that on the contrary, from a cognitive point of view, note-taking cannot be thought of as merely a simple, abbreviated transcription of information heard or read; states that working memory is an activity that is strongly dependent on central executive functions to simultaneously manage the processes of understanding, selection, and production. Kenneth, Kiewra and Kiewra (1987) state that, even during note-taking, the mental activity of the note-taker for comprehension is active, and that the revised notes produce higher success than the ones that are not. Aiken, Thomas, and Shenumm (1975) stated that note-taking can facilitate learning by causing the student to process, interpret, infer, condense, paraphrase, and provide an external memory for later use in the course content. The study examine time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ibadan.

Statement of the Problem

Poor 'academic performance of students may result to low self-esteem on the part of student, inferiority complex, student dropping out of school and as a result of this, man power development become mirage. Also, it may also lead to different anti-social behaviour of the students such as excessive drinking of alcohol, smoking, of Indian hemp, engagement in unhealthy sexual behaviour, cultist activities and other maladjustive behaviours that distract them from academic pursuit. These unhealthy behaviours of adolescents which in turn impacts poor academic performance make the researcher to ask "why are Nigerian adolescent not very concern about the current trend on their academic performance in examination? In this regard, one of the major problems of education is the students' academic failure which not only leads to the waste of current expenditure and time but also generates mental-psychological, social and family problems for the students. This problem is increasing every year so that many students cannot handle the curriculum (academic courses) or complete it in due time. Academic failure includes various aspects of educational failure such as frequent absence from classes, dropping out, repeating the grade or low quality of education.

However, researchers have tried to study different factors that could lead to poor academic performance of the students. They have researched on possible factors residents in the school, the teacher, government and the students themselves. These factors are however not enough to come into conclusion on what actually lead to poor academic performance of the students, it is on this note that the researcher is interested in factors such as time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ibadan.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to determine time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ibadan. The specific purpose are:

1. determine the relationship among time management, study environment, note-taking techniques and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan.
2. examine the joint influence of time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan.
3. determine the relative influence of time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan.

Research Question

The following three research question would be considered for this study and tested at 0.05 level of significant;

1. What is the relationship among time management, study environment, note-taking techniques and academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan?
2. What is the joint influence of time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan?
3. What is the relative influence of time management, study environment and note-taking techniques on academic performance among senior secondary school students in Ibadan?

Methodology

Research Design

The study adopted descriptive research design of correlational type and the research design was adopted because the researcher did not manipulate any variables of interest in the study. The variables were studied as they currently exist in the environment of the participants. The method is desirable because it is found useful in data collection on phenomenon that cannot be observed directly.

Population of the Study

The target population for this study consists of all senior secondary school students in Ibadan. The respondents are both male and female senior secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State.

Sample and Sampling Techniques

In this study, simple random sampling technique was used in selecting the participants. Randomly, 200 male and female senior secondary school students in Ibadan were randomly selected for the study. The researcher considered the past records of academic performance of students used and they were chosen randomly through random number digits after assigned number to them in the population inform of sampling frame. The researcher administered achievement tests to the students to obtain data on their academic performance.

Instrumentation

Four major instruments were used for data collection. The academic performance were obtained through the students' scores in the achievement test administered that was conducted by the researchers in each school. The questionnaire used in this study is divided into four (4) sections. Section A contains demographic information on personal data of the respondents i.e. gender, age range, and religion while Section B taps information on time management, Section 'C' taps information on study environment and Section 'D' taps information on note-taking techniques.

Time management Scale

Time management scale was developed by Macan, Shahani, Dipboye, & Phillips, (1990). This instrument was used to measure the process of organizing and planning how to divide your time between different activities. This scale consists of 20 items with a response format ranging from 1 Never, 2 Seldom, 3 Sometimes, 4 Usually and 5 Always. Using a five-point Likert format. Some samples of the items are: "I concentrate on only one important task at a time, but I do multiple trivial tasks at once." and "I have some time during each day when I can work uninterrupted". It has Cronbach Alpha Co-efficient which yielded 0.88.

Study Environment Questionnaire (SEQ)

Study environment Questionnaire (SEQ) was developed by Hallak (1990). This instrument was used to measure the effect of study environment on students in school. This scale consists of 14 items with a response format ranging from Strongly Agree = 5 to Strongly Disagree = 1. Using a five-point Likert format. Some samples of the items are: “Students who do feel secured in a study environment hardly achieve in their academics” and “Positive interpersonal relationships and optimal learning opportunities in a study environment can increase achievement levels of students.”. It has Cronbach Alpha Correlation Co-efficient which yielded 0.83.

Note-taking Techniques Scale

Note-taking techniques scale was developed by Zhou, & Dong, (2019). This instrument was used to measure essentially practice of recording information captured from another source. This scale consists of 16 items with a response format ranging from Strongly Agree = 5 to Strongly Disagree = 1. Using a five-point Likert format. Some samples of the items are: “When I take notes attentively, I can’t follow the logic of the speaker well” and “It’s very difficult for me to coordinate listening and note-taking concurrently”. It has Cronbach Alpha Co-efficient which yielded 0.91.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researchers obtained permission from the Ministry of Education and from the principal of each secondary schools used. The students of the chosen schools were made to know the importance of them participating in the research. The researcher further assured the respondents of the confidentiality of the information provided. The researcher gave adequate explanation to the respondents in order to ensure appropriate response were given while attending to the questionnaires. The researcher collected the questionnaires from the students after they had finished filling it and afterwards, the researcher coded the data for data analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed through the use of Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) to test the relationship between independent variables and the dependent variable and Regression analysis to test for the joint and relative contributions among the independent variables and dependent variable at 0.05 level of significant.

RESULTS

Research Question One: *Are there any significant relationship between the independent variables and dependent variable among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria.?*

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics and Correlations among the variables

	1	2	3	4
Academic Performance	1.000			
Time Management	.586**	1.000		
Study Environment	.983**	.575**	1.000	
Note-taking Technique	.243*	.221**	.081	1.000
Mean	56.240	39.290	31.620	31.620
Std. Deviation	10.894	5.091	6.841	6.841

The results from Table 1 showed that there is significant relationship between time management and academic performance ($r = 0.586$ and $p < 0.05$), study environment and academic performance and ($r = 0.983$ and $p < 0.05$) and note-taking technique and academic performance ($r = 0.243$ and $p < 0.05$) in that order.

Research Question Two: *What is the combine influence of independent variables (time management, study environment and note taking technique) on academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 2: Joint contribution of the independent variables

anagementMo	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.984 ^a	.968	.967	1.49697

ANOVA

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	6521.462	3	2173.821	1979.801	.000 ^b
Residual	215.128	196	1.098		
Total	6736.590	199			

Table 2 shows that there was the joint contribution of the independent variables (time management, study environment and note taking technique) on academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan; $R = 0.984$, $p < .05$. The table further reveals 96.7% ($Adj. R^2 = 0.967$) of the variance in the academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan were accountable for by the linear combination of the independent variables. The ANOVA results from the regression analysis show a significant contribution of the independent variables on the dependent variables; $F(3, 196) = 1979.801$, $p < 0.05$. It implies a significant joint contribution of the independent variables on academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan.

Research Question Three. *What is the relative influence of independent variables (time management, study environment and note taking technique) on academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state, Nigeria?*

Table 3: Relative Contribution of the Independent Variables on the Dependent Variable

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	Constant	2.329	1.248		1.866	.065
	TM	.550	.036	.444	5.673	.000
	SE	.267	.027	.169	2.066	.000
	NTT	.229	.014	.167	2.026	.002

Key:-> TM – Time Management, SE – Study Environment, NTT – Note Taking Technique

Table 4.3 above shows that the three independent variables contributed to academic performance among the secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state. The variables include the following: time management ($\beta = 0.444$, $t = 5.673$, $p < 0.05$); study environment ($\beta = 0.169$, $t = 2.066$, $p < 0.05$), and note taking technique ($\beta = 0.167$, $t = 2.026$, $p < 0.05$), It was observed that time management was the most potent contributor to academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo state among the selected participants for the study, while note taking technique was the least potent.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed a significant relationship between time management and academic performance among secondary school students in Ibadan, Oyo State, which contradicts the null hypothesis initially

raised. This finding implies that students who adopt effective time management strategies tend to achieve higher academic success compared to their peers who do not prioritize time management. Previous studies support this finding, emphasizing that time management helps students balance academic tasks, reduce stress, and allocate adequate time for study and other productive activities (Nasrullah and Khan, 2015). Effective time management ensures that students can meet deadlines, engage in meaningful academic exercises, and develop structured study routines. Macan et al. (1990) also noted that students with better time management skills often report lower academic stress and better academic outcomes. Therefore, the findings of this study highlight the need for schools to incorporate time management training as part of their educational programs to enhance students' academic achievement.

The study demonstrated the joint contribution of the independent variables—time management, study environment, and note-taking techniques—to the academic performance of secondary school students in Ibadan. This finding indicates that a combination of these factors creates a conducive framework that positively influences academic outcomes. According to Adeyemo (2005), a comprehensive approach that includes effective time management, a conducive study environment, and systematic note-taking techniques plays a vital role in fostering academic success. The interaction of these variables underscores the multifaceted nature of learning. When students are provided with conducive study environments, taught proper note-taking strategies, and encouraged to manage their time effectively, they are better equipped to perform well academically. These findings are consistent with the literature that emphasizes the need for an integrative approach to improving student performance (Zimmerman and Schunk, 2011).

The study further revealed that all three independent variables contributed significantly to academic performance among secondary school students in Ibadan. Among these variables, time management emerged as the most potent contributor, while note-taking techniques were the least potent. Time management emerged as the strongest predictor of academic performance. This finding is consistent with Britton and Tesser (1991), who found that students who effectively manage their time achieve better academic results. Proper time allocation helps students prioritize academic tasks, avoid procrastination, and meet learning objectives. Effective time management also fosters a sense of self-regulation, which has been linked to better learning outcomes (Zimmerman and Schunk, 2011). Study environment was identified as a significant contributor to academic performance. Research by Cheryan et al. (2014) highlighted that a well-organized and distraction-free study environment enhances students' concentration and information retention. Schools and homes that provide conducive study environments can significantly improve students' academic outcomes. This underscores the need for school administrators to invest in creating favorable learning spaces and for parents to provide quiet study environments at home. Although note-taking techniques contributed the least, they still played a crucial role in enhancing academic performance. Effective note-taking helps students retain and organize information, making it easier to review and comprehend academic content. Peverly and Wolfe (2016) emphasized that structured note-taking methods, such as the Cornell Note-Taking System, improve students' recall and comprehension. Despite being the least potent factor, note-taking remains an essential skill that supports effective learning.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that time management, study environment, and note-taking techniques significantly influenced the academic performance of senior secondary school students in Ibadan. Students who demonstrated effective time management skills, studied in conducive environments, and utilized efficient note-taking strategies consistently outperformed their peers who did not prioritize these practices. The findings underscore the need for educators, parents, and policymakers to promote and teach these essential skills to enhance students' academic outcomes. Encouraging the adoption of these strategies can help build disciplined, focused, and academically successful students who are better prepared for future educational and professional challenges. Moreover, fostering these skills during secondary school years can instill lifelong habits that contribute to personal and professional success.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of this study, the following are the recommendations:

1. Students should develop and adhere to a daily study schedule to ensure adequate time allocation for academic and extracurricular activities.
2. Teachers should integrate lessons on time management and note-taking strategies into classroom activities.
3. Parents should provide a quiet and organized space for studying at home.
4. Counsellors should offer regular workshops on study skills, including time management and note-taking techniques.
5. School management should ensure that school facilities, such as libraries and study areas, are conducive to learning.

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